

Proteomic analysis of the apoplastic fluid of contrasting cacao genotypes for resistance to Witches' Broom

Oliveira, I. B.

barbosaivina@hotmail.com
Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz

Pirovani, C. P., Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz

Gramacho, K. P., Comissão Executiva de Planejamento da Lavoura Cacauera

Santana, J. O., Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz

ASSIS, E. T. C. M., Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz

Moura, I. M., Universidade Estadual de Santa Cruz

Moniliophthora perniciosa is the hemibiotrophic fungus that causes the disease known as Witches' broom, which affects the cacao causing damage. Initially it colonizes the living cells growing in the apoplast, until it changes to its second phase, necrotrophic. The plant may release compounds into apoplast as a defense response. Therefore, the present proposal aims to elucidate the importance of apoplast in protecting the plant from pathogen attacks. For this, the apoplastic washing fluid (AWF) of two contrasting genotypes for resistance to witches' broom (CCN51 -resistant and Catongo-susceptible), under control conditions (C) and in the parasitic phase (P) of the disease, was extracted. 545 leaves of the CCN-51(C) variety and 148 of the same variety (P) were used collecting a total of 81 mL and 57 mL of AWF, respectively. The AWF was used in protein extraction and resolved on 1D SDS-PAGE, resulting in a differential yield depending on the genotype and its condition, suggesting that the plants respond to environmental variations. For the CCN-51(C), the protein yield was 1,1 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ and in the parasitic phase the disease was 3,35 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$ and the Catongo variety (C) yielded 0,46 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$. The GPX and APX enzymatic activities were also dosed. For susceptible variety there were no significant differences, however for resistant variety verified a 3X increase in APX activity. The comparative profile in 2D gels is being established. It is expected to characterize differential proteins and thus identify genes expressed in the intercellular space of cacao leaves in response to the *M. perniciosa*.

Keywords: *Proteoma, intercellular space, Theobroma cacao, plant defense.*